

Spontaneous Photographic Capture of Synchronistic Image Resemblances

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Abstract

The Jungian concept of image is pivotal to the phenomena of archetypes and synchronicity. Imagery composes the words of a non-linear language, which translates the unconscious to consciousness. However, alongside traditionally psychic images, which appear in dreams and visions, but remain largely subjective, synchronicity also encompasses so-called objective imagery, gathered not from extra-sensory, but regular sensory perception of the world and the surrounding events. Externalized imagery has been especially evident in the research of Paul Kammerer and his theory of seriality. The present research introduces a novel technique for recording and studying synchronicity and seriality through photography and narrative. The methodology of 'spontaneous photographic capture of synchronistic image resemblances' is described, using numerous visual examples from years of collected data. Each example presents an encounter with the same archetypal image, photographed in two or more causally unrelated settings, within a meaningfully close span of time and/or space. The archetypal connection in each example is identified via bundles of repeating basic percepta like number, colour, shape, angle, position, and pattern. The perceptual continuity from one setting to another is then explained in light of the spatialization of flowing time into the 4th dimension of space, or the expansion of consciousness into 5D reality. Relevant theories of electromagnetic consciousness and geomagnetism are also discussed using more specific photographic examples, which suggest that light and energy are central to the development of a more physical, and not just psychological theory of synchronicity. Finally, art's numinosity and link to the collective unconscious, as well as the importance of arts-based research methods to the study of synchronicity are emphasized.

Keywords: synchronicity, archetype, resemblance, arts-based research, art, photography, consciousness, unconscious, psyche, mind, perception, vision, image, pattern

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Introduction

Art and archetypes participate in a special connection, an intimate dance. Art pervades our lives. Humans have been viewing, experiencing, creating, and displaying it since prehistoric times. They carved stones into symbolic representations and painted images on cave walls. Thus, art and the actions relating to it are deep-seated natural instincts. As defined by the psychologist Carl Jung, an archetype too is an instinctual pattern of mind or behavior - a form that dates back to primordial times and pre-exists consciousness itself. Archetypes act spontaneously and autonomously, as if through a will of their own, crystallizing into consciousness from the unconscious, as psychic and memory images, visions and dreams, imaginations and most interestingly also, the physically actualized events of synchronicity. (Jung, 1960/2010)

Image and symbol are of course indispensable to visual art. Jung likewise utilized the concept of image to describe archetypes, although in his definition, image could also be expanded beyond the visual modality, to include a packet of symbolic information within any sensory modality. He outlined synchronicity specifically as a two-fold experience in which:

1. An unconscious image comes into consciousness in the form of a dream, idea, or premonition;
2. An objective situation coincides with this content. (Jung, 1960/2010)

We can then summarize synchronicity with a generalized formula: 'psychic image + physical image (event),' where the two images repeat some core symbolic motif. Such process is also exhibited in the extra-sensory modality of precognition, for example, where a psychic vision is followed by an event that replicates and thus clarifies the symbolism of the first image. Jung also based his theory of synchronicity on the work of a more obscure Austrian researcher, Paul Kammerer, who studied a similar phenomenon, but based on the repetition of solely physical images. 'Seriality' is what he

called a series of events, close in time, which would repetitively display the same motif. For example, a coat check ticket could display the same number as a train ticket, and then appear again elsewhere within the span of a day. (Koestler, 1971) Each such event in the physical series was more objectified so to speak, than the mental psychic images, observed only individually and subjectively.

Undoubtedly, the theme of repetition is a necessity for archetypal experience. In fact, the ancient Hermetic and alchemical philosophy, which heavily utilized symbols and images, possessed a resonant concept of resemblance. For example, the staff of the God Mercury resembled the shape of nostrils; the rocks of the world were like the bones of a man, the rivers - his veins, etc. (Foucault, 2002) Unlike the traditional mechanistic schemes of science that form causal linear chains to explain spatial relations between events, like billiard balls rolling and impacting each other, Hermeticism used the law of correspondence to draw meaningful connections between resembling image-events, otherwise completely disconnected causally.

Interestingly, a kind of doubling or repetition could also be detected in the creative process of some notable artists. Joan Miró would go to the beach in the dawn to collect random objects washed up by the tide, which he would later assemble into the most curious compositions, thus revealing their 'true personality.' (Jaffé, 1964) For him, each object possessed a double-aspect, its regular literal self, and its participation in some more metaphorical or archetypal creation. The surrealist Giorgio de Chirico likewise spoke of the common and the ghostly aspects of a thing, and Max Ernst revelled in the associations formed by two elements apparently alien to each other, such as the sewing machine and the umbrella. (Jaffé, 1964) Wassily Kandinsky stated that all things have a secret soul, and not just the stuff of poetry like the moon and the stars, but also plain things, like "a white trouser button glittering out of a puddle in the street." (Jaffé, 1964, p. 254) It is not so much the supposed beauty of objects that is of archetypal interest, but their symbolic motif, often given out by the simplest of descriptions, such as the phrase above. In archetypal phenomena, it is the

motif that repeats by unfolding into another instance of the same, but more detailed, more dimensionally deep, more complex.

Even primordial art contained an aspect of doubling. Tribal practices involved rituals of pretend-killing of an animal image, for good luck and manifestation of the same motif in the actual hunt that followed. (Jaffé, 1964) In fact, it is likely that all of thought and verbal language evolved out of this fundamental capability to transcribe a perceptual image into artistic symbol, to turn one into the other. Likewise, in highly figurative language of metaphor, the two literal inequalities that are made compatible represent the two faces of one coherent field, like the one archetype.

Methodology

The present research exhibits instances of paired images, which highlight a spontaneously repeating symbolic motif that had arisen synchronistically. Thirteen image pairs are included in this paper, out of the full collection of about 300 (Yusupova, 2025). Each pair is composed of at least one photograph taken at one time or another throughout the life of the researcher. Some of these photographs are selfies and others display nature and the surroundings. In nearly all instances, at least one of the photographs centres around some form of visual art: graffiti, painting, illustration, digital, meme, diagram, architecture, sculpture, clothing, etc. Therefore, visual art composes a suitable medium through which synchronicity can be experienced, recorded, displayed, and narrated to others.

Through its visual modality, this method also taps into the wider discipline of imagework – a set of techniques for the investigation of imagination, memory, thought, meditation, dreams, hallucinations, visualizations, etc. Traditionally, imagework has only focused on subjective imagery, using for example the projective tests of psychology. However, through its study of physical events of personally-experienced synchronicities, this research enters into the realm of exceptional human experiences (EHE's), seeking to explore the reaches of human potential. (Edgar 2004)

Each pair of images also demonstrates synchronicity in action through the corresponding personal narrative. The aim is to briefly describe the sequence of events exactly as they took place, and the manner in which the synchronistic repetition was first noticed: whether at the moment of the experience or some time afterwards; whether the two images were juxtaposed in space and/or time; and whether the resemblance was a true synchronicity, or more of an association to a memory. While the credibility of the narrative cannot always be ascertained directly by others, perhaps the bundles of resemblances within each image-pair can speak for themselves, revealing meaningful causally-improbable patterns in their own visual language. The narratives also discuss philosophical, psychological, and scientific insights that have emerged alongside the experiences.

This method of research makes use of participation mystique – an intuitive experiential knowing that results from the mystical encounter between the self and the environment. (Heron & Reason, 1997) One definitive characteristic of such intuitive and transpersonal inquiries is the researcher's impulse and passion towards understanding a particular topic of interest, often exemplified through the telling of personal life stories. (Andersen & Braud, 2011) As such, autoethnography (Adams & Jones, 2018) is utilized in that all instances recount events from the researcher's daily life, accompanied by personal photographs. The major topics of interest however are the wider workings of synchronicity, the collective unconscious, and consciousness.

Such a participatory arts-based research technique cannot necessarily follow the rigid scientific format of experimentation. One major difference is the difficulty in pre-setting a hypothesis prior to obtaining results. Archetypes are notoriously autonomous, and can rarely be manipulated by the conscious will. (Johnson, 1986) They are not lab specimens to be selected and readily brought to light. Nor do they follow linear temporal causality, as does the experimental method. It is nearly impossible to force a specific archetype to reveal itself, but is easier to humbly remain ready to observe the ones that do happen to manifest when they do. Thus, as is explained in

the first instance in the findings below, this particular method of research developed itself spontaneously. Experiences simply started occurring, without any predetermined intention on the researcher's part to make them happen. Only after several such experiences, did the specific image-doubling method begin to elucidate itself. For this reason also, there is no specific research question prior to any of the findings below, except for the most general 'What meanings does this archetypal experience suggest?' This drastic openness and receptivity to spontaneity however will be challenged in later research, which will aim to enter into co-creation with the collective unconscious, and study the way in which we might be able to influence specific archetypes to channel through this method after all.

Findings

Figure 1

As Above, So Below

This was my very first occurrence of photographic synchronicity. One day, I noticed this freshly painted mural, shown here on the left (Wijayasinha, 2021), while biking through my city. About half an hour later back at my house, I was shocked by the view of the storm brewing outside

my window, shown here on the right. The juxtaposition of the bright pink and purple colours, and the same angle in the line in the clouds created an uncanny resemblance between the art and the natural scene. It felt as if the synchronicity was communicating a deeper message, that of the alchemical dictum “As above, so below.” (Atkinson, 2011)

The storm turned into a tornado that touched down in a nearby city. For this reason, the connection between the raw power of nature and the collective unconscious was palpably felt. Jung defined the collective unconscious as the psychic substratum that houses the archetypes. (1960/2010) This experience eventually led me to consider geomagnetic fields and the Schumann Resonance as possible energetic and holographic storage sources for the collective unconscious. While human biofields and electromagnetic theories of consciousness are gaining prominence in modern consciousness studies (McCraty, 2016; McFadden, 2023), the larger fields of nature could account for the more exteriorized phenomena of synchronicity that extend outside the body. As the scientist Rupert Sheldrake would say, the memory of nature is stored in morphogenetic fields. (1988/2012) Carl Jung and the famous quantum physicist Wolfgang Pauli, working together in a 26 year collaboration, compared the archetype in a similar manner to a field of energy. (1932-1958/2001)

From then on, experiences of repetitive images continued to occur, eventually developing into this method, where two or more images are collaged side by side, to draw emphasis on their spontaneous visual resemblances. In this next instance, on the left is a photo of me one morning before going kayaking. Later that same afternoon, I visited Greektown and noticed this mural of the goddess Athena, shown on the right (Usquiano, 2021). Later that evening, when I saw the two photos side by side in my phone’s photo gallery, the resemblances jumped out to attention. We are both standing in the same pose and holding a long spear-like object in the left hand. In my opinion, this is a prime example of an archetype channeling through unconsciously, as I had no conscious

knowledge that I would encounter the resembling image of Athena when I had posed for my kayaking photo.

Figure 2

Athena

One of the main definitions of an archetype developed by Carl Jung was that of a mythological character or personage. Many of my photographic synchronicities began to embody such beings. For example, on the left in Figure 3 is an illustration of an angel made by a friend (Tirone, 2014), which I included in my poetry book. On the right is a photo that was once taken of me on my bicycle. Notice the bundle of resemblances, which are the tunnel with light, the angled position of the body, a headband or a headpiece, and stripes everywhere, such as on my shirt, pants, the angel's scarf, the bicycle spokes, and the tunnel.

Figure 3*Angel*

It is not always that the two images are separated by a short period of time. These two images were separated by years when they were created, yet the resemblances were still only noticed in a close alignment in space. At the time, I was browsing through my photographs on my computer, while my poetry book happened to be resting on the table beside me, open to the particular page with the illustration. A great variety exists in how these juxtapositions jump out to attention in the first place – whether the unconscious connection is noticed at the moment that the photo is taken, an hour later, or a year later.

Figure 4

Witch

I used to practice the martial art of Muay Thai. In this next example, the photo on the left was taken after I had won a fight. On the right is the artwork of a magical being (Chew, c. 2018), which I've had framed in my house for a long time. What was becoming obvious is that there was always some form of visual art involved in the archetypal doubles. In my opinion, this speaks of the immense numinous power, which infuses into the art-making process and creates a definitive imprint on the field of the collective unconscious.

Notice again the connecting motifs like the light green tanktop, patterns on the bottoms – the shorts and the skirt, the potpourri of things both in the art and on the elephant on my shirt, the overall greyish-green colour of the artwork and the wall behind me, and us standing in a similar pose, and holding an important object in our right hands. Disciplines like neuroscience, psychology, philosophy, and graphic design study the nature of perceptual categories such as these because they

draw attention to the way the mind forms wholes. Graphic mapping techniques also use correspondences between visual variables such as these to encode information. (Bertin, 1967/1983) Thus, these cases might be displaying a form of communication from some more encompassing pansychic form of intelligence, which operates through the unconscious.

Figure 5

Devil Child

There are times you can concretely feel this intelligence, even decipher some characteristic of its personality. In this funny example, I was once visiting New York City and took this selfie on the right. About a month later, while browsing through the photos of that trip, I noticed how the two brown direction signs on the bike trail behind me have aligned precisely to form horns on my head. Even more hilarious is that the day after this photo was taken, I purchased this tank top of the devil child from a vintage store, shown on the left. There is an obvious repetition of the horns, the colour

red, the position of the body that is same, just reflected along the vertical axis, and even the same look in our eyes. Whatever it was that caused the image of the devil child to be retrocausally channeled through my photo the day before certainly had a sense of humour.

Figure 6

Ganesh

It is not only through selfies that these entities come through. Here for example, on the left is a public artwork that was displayed downtown Toronto (Larriviere, Pasfield & Burgess, 2024). On the right is the digital version of a divination card (Moses, 2023) that popped up on social media about half an hour after I saw the previous installation. The resemblances that jumped out were the purple and blue shawl on Ganesh and the same colours in the curve of the bubble, the roundness of the bubbles and the mandala behind the deity's head, and the stocky posture of Ganesh repeating

the installation shape itself, from the particular perspective of my photo. It is natural to feel mystical guidance when a well-known spiritual deity and a corresponding inspirational message are delivered through the synchronicity.

Figure 7

The Scream

It is always special to receive synchronistic instances of famous artworks because of their immense cultural significance. The photo on the bottom shows an orange leaf I once saw while on a hike in the forest. It reminded me of a face, so I snapped a picture of it. Now for one reason or another, I also happened to have 'The Scream' by Edvard Munch (1893) downloaded on my phone. A few days later, this alignment of one image on top of another in my phone gallery was what specifically drew out the resemblance. Do you see how the V-shaped tree branches align perfectly with the dark shapes in the background of the painting? The screaming face and the orange leaf align precisely along a vertical axis. Even the thinner branch on the right seems to match the curve in the water, and the large green leaf on the left vaguely resembles the space of the bridge's floor.

These resemblances may have never been noticed had the images not happened to spontaneously sit one on top of another in this way in my phone gallery. It is a wonder how the downloaded art could have somehow permeated my unconscious field and channeled through in such a way that I then took a photo of the orange leaf from that precise and perfect perspective. The operation of the unconscious through the series of events such as these is simply mind-boggling.

The recent wildfires in Canada have been producing large amounts of smoke in the air the past few summers. I took the photo on the left in Figure 8 one early morning at sunrise, when the sun had a blazing red colour due to the smoke acting like a filter. Earlier that week, I happened to read the essay on dimensionality 'On Modern Art' by the famous painter Paul Klee. Thus, something intuitively told me to look up some of his art. As I did so, I found one that resembled my photograph, shown here on the right (Klee, 1930). There is the greyish atmosphere, the red sun, and the prominence of the tower sticking up just underneath it.

Figure 8

Red Sun

Figure 9

Orange Sun

Figure 9 shows the second photo I took of the sun on the same morning. Likewise, there was a resembling painting by Paul Klee (1922), shown on the right. The repeating elements are the orange circle in the middle, and the particular-shaped air-space between the two trees in the photograph, and the two buildings in the art. Apparently, Klee included big red and orange circles as focal points in many of his artworks.

Figure 10

Numeral IX

One night I was drawn to the way the rain drops were creating beautiful paths in my photos. On the left is one of those photos that had captured the blue paths in the shape of the Roman numeral IX. Half an hour later, I stumbled upon this building nearby and somehow noticed the lit-up neon sign at the top. It too displayed the same Roman numeral IX and also had blue lines. There is a

bundling of several variables like colour and shape in one photo, and a spatial separation of these same variables in the other. To me this resonates with the binding and differentiating properties of consciousness and perception (Schmidt, 2009), which in my opinion form some of the more relevant and interesting topics in consciousness studies. Once again, the properties of energy are ones that can both entangle and decohere in a comparable manner. (Quanta, 2021)

Figure 11

5D

Here is another good example of binding and differentiation of visual variables. On the left is a meme I encountered on social media. (Unknown Artist, 2025) On the right is an old photo that I was immediately reminded of. My T-shirt has the exact same tie-dye pattern as the planet. The colours of this pattern are also dispersed throughout my photo. The roundness of the planet is

repeated by my earring, which baby Vivian is holding up, as if for emphasis. The two light splotches on the planet are also similarly angled by the two light splotches on the wall behind me. Therefore, there are repetitions of pattern, colours, shape, and position bundled into one object in the artwork, and diffused throughout different objects in the photo.

The observation of visual variables bound into an object in one photo, and dispersed into several objects in the other, persists through many separate examples. In fact, we can envision looking through a kind of lens on which the trace of the original image is inscribed. If we then look through this lens into a new setting, the inscribed image traces onto the new context like an applied filter. This is the hypothetical essence of archetypal projection. The lens or filter on which traces are inscribed could then be some form of energetic medium that permeates the fabric of spacetime – something like the ‘ether’ of the ancients (Jung, 1968), the subtle energies of Vedic and esoteric philosophies, or perhaps the electromagnetic fields that pervade the universe.

Additionally, the connection in this example was certainly more of a memory than a synchronicity. However, a synchronicity is in essence also a memory. When the viewer sees the second image, they then remember the first, just not from so long ago as in associative memory. In fact, the examples presented thus far should elucidate that synchronicity exists on a spectrum with memory. Indeed, Carl Jung defined the collective unconscious as the substratum of mind that contained the universal memories of humanity, also known as the archetypes. (Jung, 1959)

Figure 12 on the left shows a photograph I once took while hiking. On the right is a new painting by the famous visionary artist, Alex Grey (2024), that appeared in the stream on social media a few minutes later. The resemblances are the golden flowers, the sun rays radiating outwards from the centre, even the tip of my thumb peeping into my photo and the presence of hands in the painting.

Figure 12

Golden Flower

A few months later, when recounting this experience in one of my classes, I suddenly noticed the small luminous artifact which looked like a blue eye under the branch. It matched the eyes in the tip of the paintbrush and the myriad fractalized eyes within the golden flower in the painting. Thus, the higher level meaning of this experience emerged as the emphasis on holography, including light itself proposed as a medium for symbolic communication. From then on, the method began to transmit more of such photographic light artifacts in the shape of significant symbols.

In this final example in Figure 13, I was in my friend's room that had a spinning lightbulb projecting moving colourful circles onto the wall. One of the pink circular lights hit the corner of the wall and split into a pink heart, just as I snapped the photo. I also happened to be wearing a heart symbol on my shirt. On the left is a divination card I pulled earlier that day. It shows my favorite

angel from that deck – the Angel of Heart’s Desire (NewAgeStore, 2018). The connecting motifs are the colours pink and purple, and the heart floating to the top left of the body. The heart symbol is one that I see most frequently in synchronicities.

Figure 13

Hologram Heart

Conclusion

The method of ‘spontaneous photographic capture of synchronistic image resemblances,’ which has been presented here integrates several arts-based modalities of research. There is an obvious reliance on pre-existent visual art of all types, created by various artists, and the implementation of the researcher’s own photography and narrative descriptions. In addition, the method is autoethnographic (Adams & Holman Jones, 2018), as cases are based on events in the

researcher's personal life; and a/r/tographic (Schultz & Legg, 2020), because it collages various images together and draws out theoretical insights that help elucidate and present complex topics in consciousness studies. In this sense, the possibility of successfully merging art with scientific and philosophical inquiry is demonstrated.

The methodology is also phenomenological and participatory, in that it centres around the personal psychological valuations and associations of the researcher, rather than discarding them, as in traditional methods of quantitative science. This is an example of intuitive and organic inquiry that make sense of the whole self in niche with the environment. (Anderson & Braud, 2011) Here thrive philosophies beyond linear causality, such as the acausal logic of archetypes and the Hermetic doctrines of resemblance and correspondence (Foucault, 2002; Atkinson, 1908/2011).

The involvement of art does not need imply vagueness and non-verbal knowing. For example, the method makes evident a certain clarity and rigor of thinking in identifying and outlining the specific visual variables that repeat, such as colour, number, shape, orientation, pattern, and motif. However, it has been suggested in the semiology of graphics that at most three such variables can be identified in one moment of perception. So when a set of images contains more than three resemblances, longer perceptual time and effort is needed to precisely place them all. (Bertin, 1983) We thus enter the realm of cognition, rather than direct perception. However, even before the necessary time has been given to such a symbolic analysis and all the resembling variables have been properly identified, what often draws one's attention to the paired images is a vague but potent feeling. Without yet crystallized thoughts or words, the images somehow communicate the potential archetypal meaning within them radiating outwards, urging us to decipher it. Hence, the strange repetition of the whole bundle of variables must somehow be noted first by the unconscious, before it is even transcribed into conscious perception and words.

The aim of arts-based research is to create new ways of seeing, thinking, and communicating. (Leavy, 2018) Unlike verbal language that strings together words in linear sentences, the language of visual imagery has the advantage of integrating symbolic complexity in a networked way, compacted into the space of the image or the image set. This then gives emergence to metaphors that can correlate drastically different settings and contexts between the images. This correlation from one image to the other may be interpreted theoretically in several ways. For one, it may be solely a product of the interpreter's cognitive meaning-making processes - the result of a kind of 'hypercognition,' as is observed in pareidolia and apophenia (Reddy et al, 2018). The question then becomes why and how does meditation give rise to this mental state, as it did here? Research shows that meditative techniques work to induce energetic coherence in the heart, brain, and biofields of the body. (McCraty, 2016) Could such an energetic coherence have also spurred the intensification of pattern recognition capabilities in the mind?

The phenomenologist Jean Gebser theorized that humanity's consciousness had evolved through a series of structures of increasing dimensionality. The early humans lived in a one-dimensional world, not differentiating between the world out there and the self in here. Gradually through a series of evolutionary steps, humans then evolved the ability to project their awareness into the three dimensions of space we see today. (Gebser, 1949/1985) According to this model of expansion, consciousness is set to continue to expand into higher dimensionalities. Gebser's latest integral structure is characterized by fluid atemporality and networks of meaning, allowing the ability to observe something through multiple perspectives at the same time. (Gebser, 1949/1985) Similarly, this methodology illustrates the viewing of the same motif through pairs of different images and events.

We can then define the archetype as an object of not just 3 dimensions, but 4 or more. What is being viewed through these experiences, in a more expanded cognitive way, are the virtual multi-

dimensional archetypal fields. Such objects extends continuously through time from the moment of event-image 1 to the moment of event-image 2, in the same way that a regular 3D object extends continuously through the space that it occupies. Therefore, time is spatialized into the 4th dimension of space. Yet, the flow of time or consciousness itself can never be depleted, but simply ascends into the 5th dimension, as it remains expanding and creating more and more spatial dimensions. Thus, the archetypal eye offers glimpses of a higher-dimensional reality, and the method of photographic image resemblances introduced here presents one prospect for observing, recording and analyzing these 5D perceptions.

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